

Mob Grazing in Agroforestry systems

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Meadows divided into small plots through intra-field agroforestry at Ferme des Pâtures.

Mob grazing is based on dividing pastures into small plots, with a high instantaneous stocking rate and short grazing periods (from 0.5 to 4 days) to improve both the quantity and quality of grass. Ferme des Pâtures is a farm specializing in organic sheep dairy and beef cattle production. The farm practices mob grazing combined with a rotation of temporary pastures, crops, and alfalfa. In the spring, it uses fixed paddocks with rotation cycles ranging from 1 to 4 days. In summer, it applies the "front wire" technique on alfalfa once or twice a day. This system allows the 115 ewes and 20 Aberdeen Angus cattle to meet their nutritional needs while optimizing pasture regeneration. In 2016, the farm planted rows of trees every 26 meters, oriented north-south, across 17 hectares. Then, in 2022, it added 1,100 trees and shrubs (windbreak hedges and umbrella trees). In 2023, an additional 700 meters of intra-parcel agroforestry and 200 meters of windbreaks were established. Ferme des Pâtures selected a mix of forage tree species and timber trees, including hybrid elm, ash, small-leaf and large-leaf lime, black locust, service tree, alder, and others. The integration of agroforestry into this system helps divide the pastures into small plots for implementing mob grazing, replacing temporary stakes. Agroforestry in this context also improves soil fertility and structure through controlled trampling and the incorporation of organic residues. Thanks to these practices, the farm observes better yields in its pastures—reaching 6 to 7 tons of dry matter in temporary pastures, 3 to 4 tons in permanent pastures, and up to 10 tons in grazed alfalfa. The choice to preserve soil structure and support microbial life led to their decision to discontinue tillage, which contributed to these results.

Camille Archambaud

*Ver de Terre Production and
ADAN (Association for Agroforestry
Dynamics in Normandy)*

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